

A-site cation engineering in two-dimensional Ruddlesden-Popper $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films

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ABSTRACT

The partial incorporation of large organic cations into the octahedral sites of the three-dimensional (3D) perovskites (A-site cation engineering) has been widely investigated in films to optimize the performance of solar cell devices. However, the very few works reporting on the addition of large organic A-site cations in two-dimensional (2D) Ruddlesden-Popper (RP) perovskites have focused their attention on single crystals with low dimensionality ($n = 2$ and 3). Here, we have studied the gradual substitution of the methylammonium (MA) cation in thin films of 2D RP perovskites $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (BA = *n*-butylammonium) by guanidinium (Gua), dimethylammonium (DA), ethylammonium (EA), rubidium (Rb), propylammonium (PA), cesium (Cs) or formamidinium (FA) to synthesize mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites. Our experimental results allow us to determine the percentage limit at which the A-site cation is homogeneously incorporated in all n phases without destabilizing the overall structure. We also define two different Goldschmidt tolerance factors for each inserted A-cation to estimate the threshold value. Grazing Incidence Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (GIWAXS) measurements reveal the loss of the preferential orientation of the crystallites in the films at percentages above the threshold. The addition of percentages above the limit reveals the preferential insertion of the A-cation in the low dimensional phases ($n = 2$ and 3) with relaxed Goldschmidt tolerance factors. The steady-state and time-resolved absorption and photoluminescence (PL) measurements show that the structural changes in the 2D RP perovskites may lead to modifications of the optoelectronic properties as larger bandgap (with EA), blue-shift of the PL peak position (above the threshold), strong quenching of the PL (with Cs) or reduced concentration of trap states (with Gua and EA). The extensive characterization of the newly prepared mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskite films can be very valuable to correlate the size and shape of the A-cation with the changes of the properties. Finally, solar devices were fabricated with the different mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites obtaining an enhanced performance in the films with 10% of Gua or EA.

Introduction

Two-dimensional (2D) hybrid halide Ruddlesden-Popper (RP) perovskites with general formula $A'_{2}A_{n-1}B_{n}X_{3n+1}$ where A, A' and B are cations and X is a halogen, constitute a unique family of low dimensional materials lately employed in many optoelectronic applications.¹⁻¹² The structure of the 2D RP perovskites is composed of layers of inorganic octahedra (BX_6) that are interconnected by a wide variety of organic cations (A'), as for example phenylethylammonium (PEA), butylammonium (BA), pentylammonium (PA), hexylammonium (HA) or benzylammonium (BzA).¹³⁻²⁰ The large organic cations balance the negative charge of the inorganic framework maintaining the charge neutrality condition in the entire structure.²¹ Importantly, the number of inorganic layers (n value) that are packed between the organic cations determines the optoelectronic properties of the material with strong exciton confinement for $n < 5$ in opposition to the low exciton binding energy for high n values.^{22,23} Single crystals of the 2D RP perovskites with a fixed thickness of the inorganic layers (uniform n value through the entire crystal) have easily been synthesized but the formation of phase-pure 2D RP films is not straightforward.²⁴⁻²⁶ Thus, the solution methods typically employed for the preparation of perovskite films provide a mixture of phases with different inorganic layer thicknesses due to thermodynamic mixing.^{27,28}

Concerning the A-site, the typically employed cation is methylammonium (MA) which is incorporated into the octahedral voids existing in the inorganic framework.²⁹⁻³³ The size limitation of the A-cation imposed by the octahedra network is experimentally defined in the three dimensional (3D) hybrid halide perovskites (ABX_3) by the Goldschmidt tolerance factor, $t = \frac{r_A+r_X}{\sqrt{2}(r_B+r_X)}$ where r_A , r_B and r_X are the effective radii of the A- and B-cation and X-anion, respectively. Thus, the tolerance factor must range from 0.8 to 1.0 in lead iodide 3D perovskites to obtain stable crystal structures and only three cations fulfil this condition: methylammonium, formamidinium (FA) and cesium (Cs). However, the application of the previously defined Goldschmidt tolerance factor in the 2D RP perovskites is not appropriate and the concept of relaxation of the tolerance factor in 2D RP perovskites has recently emerged.^{17,34-37}

Thus, the synthesis of single crystals of 2D RP perovskites ($n = 2$ or 3) incorporating in the A-site large organic cations which lie outside the tolerance

factor range has been published.^{17,34-37} The guanidinium cation (Gua) with a tolerance factor of $t = 1.03$ has been fully inserted into the octahedral voids of layered structures with $n = 2$ using pentylammonium (PA) or hexylammonium (HA) as the A'-cation ($\text{PA}_2\text{GuaPb}_2\text{I}_7$ and $\text{HA}_2\text{GuaPb}_2\text{I}_7$).^{4,17} Colloidal nanoplates of a series of 2D RP perovskites with $n = 2$ and HA as the A' cation have been also synthesized with up to seven different A-cations demonstrating the flexibility of these low dimensional layered structures.³⁶ Single crystals of the $\text{BA}_2\text{EA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite ($n = 3$, EA = ethylammonium, $t = 1.03$) have also been synthesized.³⁵ Moreover, the formation of single crystals of mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{EA}_x\text{MA}_{1-x})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskites ($x = 0-1$) has been proved which reveals that the inorganic framework tolerates the large octahedral distortions caused by two A-cations with different size and shape.³⁵ Recently, single crystals of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{A})\text{Pb}_2\text{I}_7$ perovskites with A = MA, FA, Gua or DA (Dimethylammonium) have been synthesized exhibiting the effect of the A-site cation on the properties of the perovskites.³⁷ Regarding the preparation of films, we have recently reported the formation of mixed A-cation $(\text{PEA})_2(\text{MA}_x\text{Gua}_{1-x})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskites in a wide range of Gua percentage and with a notable impact on the distribution of the n -members and, therefore on the optoelectronic properties of the films.³⁴ Thus, there is a lack of a general study to investigate the sort of A-cations that can be incorporated in 2D RP films and their impact on the optoelectronic properties.

In this article, we explore the changes caused by the substitution of the MA cation by other A-site cations in the crystal structure of a thin film of 2D RP perovskites. The incorporation of A-cations with a variety of sizes and shapes in the mixture of phases with different n values of a film is studied as a function of the percentage of the added cation. By using only geometrical factors, the Goldschmidt rule is redefined in perovskites containing two types of A-site cations taking into account the deformation in the crystal lattice through the changes in the Pb-I-Pb angle. The maximum percentage of the large A-cation that can be incorporated into the octahedral voids without modifying the distribution of n phases in the films can be predicted with the modified tolerance factor.

We have accomplished a comprehensive investigation by mixing the archetypal methylammonium (MA) cation with six different A-cations (Guanidinium, Gua; Ethylammonium, EA; Cesium, Cs; Rubidium, Rb; Dimethylammonium, DA;

Propylammonium, PA and Formamidinium, FA) together with butylammonium (BA) as the large A'-cation to synthesize mixed A-cation (BA)₂(MA_{1-x}A_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ 2D RP perovskites. The study includes the whole mixing range between both cations with variations of 5-10% which allows us to determine the gradual formation of specific *n* phases. Both X-ray diffraction measurements and absorption spectroscopy are utilized to identify the changes in the crystal lattice and distribution of the phases. Photoluminescence measurements together with time-resolved absorption and emission spectroscopy reveal the effect of each A-cation on the optoelectronic properties of the material, shedding light into the structure-property relationship of 2D RP perovskites.

Experimental Section

Starting materials. Lead iodide 99% (PbI₂), *n*-Butylammonium iodide 98% (BAI), Ethylammonium iodide 98% (EAI), Dimethylammonium iodide 98% (DAI), *n*-Propylammonium iodide 98% (PAI), Cesium iodide 99.999% (CsI), Rubidium iodide 99.9% (RbI), Titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) solution (75% in 2-propanol), Lithium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI), 4-*tert*-butylpyridine (TBP), Cobalt(III) FK209 TFSI, Spiro-MeOTAD, Acetonitrile (ACN) 99.9% were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Methylammonium iodide 98% (MAI), Guanidinium iodide 99% (GuaI) and Formamidinium iodide 98% (FAI) were purchased from Great Cell Solar. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (DMF) 99.8% Extra Dry over Molecular Sieve, AcroSeal and chlorobenzene extra dry over molecular sieve, AcroSeal were purchased from Acros Organics. TiO₂ paste (DSL 30NR-D, batch 438) and Ethanol Absolute Dry (max. 0.02% water) were supplied by Dyesol and PanReac AppliChem, respectively. The glass patterned with fluorine tin oxide (FTO) TEC-15 and amorphous glass were purchased from Pilkington. Soap (decon90) and isopropyl alcohol (technical grade, 99.5%) were purchased from Decon and PanReac AppliChem, respectively. All starting materials for the synthesis were commercially purchased and used as received.

Film fabrication method. FTO and amorphous glass were cleaned by a sequential sonication treatment in Decon 90, Milli-Q water and isopropyl alcohol. The substrates were treated with ultraviolet ozone for 15 min before the deposition. To facilitate the subsequent deposition of the perovskite, a 60 nm

thick mesoporous TiO₂ layer was prepared by spin coating on the FTO a dilute dispersion of TiO₂ in ethanol, 1:8 by weight ratio, at 2000 rpm for 15 s. After drying at 100 °C for 10 min, the TiO₂ mesoporous layer was heated at 500 °C for 30 min and later cooled to room temperature.^{39,40}

Perovskite precursor solutions. Stoichiometric precursor solutions were prepared by mixing PbI₂, MAI, BAI and AI in 0.5 ml of DMF following the steps detailed in our previous work.³⁴ All solutions were filtered by a 0.22 µm pore size, hydrophobic PTFE membrane.

Perovskite deposition. The perovskite films have been deposited by the hot casting (HC) temperature method.³⁴ The substrates were heated at 90 °C for 10 min. Then, they were moved quickly on the spin coater and 70 µl of the precursor solution was deposited on the substrates at 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. The films were annealed at 100 °C on a hot plate for 20 minutes.

Device Fabrication. Perovskite solar cells were fabricated on FTO substrates. Before the deposition, the substrates were cleaned by a sequential sonication treatment. The TiO₂ blocking layer (30 nm in thickness) was deposited onto the FTO glass substrate by spray pyrolysis, using a titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) solution in ethanol (60% v/v). For de formation of anatase phase, the TiO₂ compact layer was then kept at 450 °C for 30 min.⁴¹ The mesoporous TiO₂ layer (200 nm in thickness) was deposited by spin coating at 2000 rpm for 15 s using a diluted TiO₂ dispersion in ethanol, ratio 1:8 by weight, followed by a sintering step at 500 °C for 30 min. An additional doping treatment using Li⁺ ions (10.04 mg LiTFSI in 1 ml acetonitrile, 35 mM) was used for the TiO₂ mesoporous layer prior to perovskite deposition.⁴² The perovskite films were deposited by the hot casting (HC) temperature method as indicated above. After this time, spiro-OMeTAD was spin coated at 4000 rpm, for 30 s from a chlorobenzene solution (28.9 mg in 400 µL) containing LiTFSI (7.0 µL from a 520 mg mL⁻¹ stock solution in acetonitrile), TBP (11.5 µL), and Co(III)TFSI (8.8 µL from a 40 mg mL⁻¹ stock solution) as dopants. Finally, a 70 nm gold electrode was deposited as a metallic contact by thermal evaporation (1·10⁻⁶ torr.)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. The XRD patterns of the films were performed using a D8 DISCOVER diffractometer from Bruker operating at 40 kV and 40 mA and using Cu Kα radiation (1.54060 Å). The range of measurement was done from 2 to 40 ° Bragg angles.

GIWAXS measurements. GIWAXS measurements were performed in a Bruker Discover diffractometer equipped with a Cu microsource with a 1 mm pinhole collimator, an eulerian cradle and an area detector Pilatus 100K. A 2θ range between 10-50 degrees was used.

UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy. The measurement of UV-Visible absorption spectra was performed at room temperature (~ 25 °C) using a Cary 100 UV-VIS spectrophotometer in the range of 400-800 nm in all cases.

Scanning Electron Microscopy studies. For the morphology characterization, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image of the films were performed using a JEOL JSM 7800F microscope working at 2 kV. The work distances were ~ 6.6 mm for all cases and 2000X magnification. Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) was performed using a Silicon Drift Detector (Oxford Instruments).

Steady-state and time-resolved PL measurements. Steady-state photoluminescence spectra were recorded with a FLS980 (Edinburgh Instruments) photoluminescence spectrometer using a 450 W Xenon arc lamp and a R298P photomultiplier as detector. Time resolved fluorescence measurements were accomplished through the time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) technique, by using the same FLS980 (Edinburgh Instruments) photoluminescence spectrometer. The samples were excited at 406.4 nm with an 86.8 ps pulse width diode laser using a R2658P photomultiplier as the detector.

PL quantum yield measurements. The PLQYs were measured using an integrating sphere coupled to an FLS980 photoluminescence spectrometer. The FLS980 was equipped with double monochromators, a 450 W Xenon lamp and a PMT-R2658P detector. A neutral density filter (OD = 3) was placed in the emission path in order to measure excitation region of the spectrum without detector saturation effects.

Transient absorption measurements. Femtosecond transient absorption measurements were performed using a broadband pump-probe transient absorption spectrometer (HELIOS, Ultrafast Systems). The pump light was generated using a regenerative Ti: Sapphire amplifier (Spitfire Ace, Spectra Physics, 1 kHz) that provides ultra-short pulses of high power at 800 nm. This system requires a seed laser to provide the input pulses and a pump laser to energize the amplifier. The regenerative amplifier is seeded using a Ti: Sapphire

femtosecond laser (MaiTai SP, Spectra Physics, 80 MHz) and pumped by a diode-pumped Q-switched laser of Nd: YLF (Empower 45, Spectra Physics, 1 kHz). The amplified radiation (800 nm, 100fs, 5W) is divided into two beams. The first one is used to pump a tunable optical parametric amplifier (TOPAS prime, Spectra Physics) in the range 290-1600 nm that generates the excitation of the sample and the second one is employed to generate white light for the absorption of the sample. In the Helios spectrometer, the UV-VIS white light continuum generated by focusing the fundamental light from the amplifier on a thin CaF₂ crystal after the controlled optical delay (3.3 ns), was used as a probe beam, directed to the sample and detected with a CMOS sensor. The pump pulse was chopped by a mechanical chopper synchronized to one-half of the laser repetition rate, resulting in a pair of the spectra, with and without the pump, from which the absorption change induced by the pump pulse was estimated.

Device characterization. The photovoltaic device performance was analysed using a Oriel LSH-7320 ABA LED Solar Simulator producing 1 Sun AM 1.5 (1,000Wm⁻²) sunlight. Current–voltage curves were measured with a Keithley 2400 potentiostat at a reverse scan rate of 100 mV/s, 1000 mV/s and 10000 mV/s, and a sweep delay of 20 seconds. The solar cells were masked with a metal aperture of 0.09 cm² to define the active area. The cells were measured in air, at room temperature and without encapsulation.

Results

Thin films of the reference $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ and the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Ax})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskites were prepared by using the hot casting (HC) temperature (90 °C) and spin coating methods. The detailed conditions of the preparation of the films can be found in the experimental section. Briefly, dimethylformamide (DMF) has been used as the solvent to prepare the precursor solutions with an initial concentration of 0.6 M in PbI_2 and stoichiometric ratio for all other precursors (BAI, MAI and AI). Figure S1A exhibits the experimental X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of a $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ film together with the simulated XRD pattern of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite obtained from crystallographic data.¹⁸ The XRD pattern of the film displays only two sharp peaks: a very intense Bragg reflection at 28.32° and a weak peak (less than 10% intensity) at 14.04° , which reveals the high crystallinity of the 2D RP perovskites in the film. The comparison with the simulated XRD pattern allows us to assign both peaks to the (202) and (111) planes, respectively. In the 3D perovskites, the previous XRD peaks are assigned to the (110) and (220) planes. The presence of only one major reflection peak in the XRD pattern proves the preferential orientation of the 2D RP phase in the film. Thus, the (202) crystallographic plane is horizontally oriented to the substrate which involves that the BA layers lay down parallel to the mesoporous TiO_2 layer. This arrangement of the 2D RP perovskites is highly beneficial to improve the charge transport through the film for optoelectronic applications.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸ Figure S1B shows the absorption spectrum for the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ film exhibiting the typical exciton bands related to the 2D RP phases with $n = 2$ (570 nm), $n = 3$ (605 nm), $n = 4$ (640 nm) and an absorption onset around 760 nm associated to the RP phases with high n values close to $n = \infty$. The presence of various absorption signals indicates the existence of a distribution of phases in the film (crystalline domains with different n values) in opposition to the situation in a single crystal where a homogeneous RP phase with a defined n value is synthesized. This remarkable singularity between both synthetic methods together with the greater applicability of the films compared to the single crystals is the main motivation to carry out this investigation on the

influence of the incorporation of different types of A-cations into the structure of the 2D RP perovskites in thin films.

Scheme 1. Sketch of the replacement of the MA cation in the $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite by the different A-site cations, Rb, Cs, DA, EA, Gua and PA, to form the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$.

Structural characterization of the mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskite films

The incorporation of the different A-cations to the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite has been performed by replacing the same percentage of the MA cation with guanidinium (Gua), dimethylammonium (DA), ethylammonium (EA), propylammonium (PA), rubidium (Rb), cesium (Cs) or formamidinium (FA) in the precursor solution to move from 0% ($\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$) to 100% ($\text{BA}_2\text{A}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$) in the novel A-cation (see Scheme 1). The amount of BA1 and PbI_2 is maintained constant for all solutions. Figure 1 and S2 display the normalized XRD patterns of the mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites where the addition of a limited but variable amount of the A-site cations does not either produce additional Bragg peaks or largely modify the shape and position of the initial reflections of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite film. Figure 2 shows the XRD patterns in logarithmic scale for each mixed A-cation perovskite film where the appearance of new reflection peaks can be easily detected. The percentage of the A-cation at which additional Bragg peaks are noticed corresponds to 25%, 10%, 30%, 5%, 15% and 80% for the Gua, DA, EA, PA, Rb and Cs cations, respectively. The effect of the addition of the A-cation on the structure of the 2D RP perovskites in the films

can be then separated into two parts delimited by the threshold values observed in Figure 3. The rest of the experimental techniques corroborates this double behavior, specifically the steady-state absorption measurements. Thus, at percentages of the A-cation below the threshold, the preservation of the original XRD pattern of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite indicates that the inorganic framework is capable of incorporating the A-cations homogeneously within all the different n phases with only minor structural changes. Above these percentages, the presence of additional peaks is related to the formation of other crystalline structures different to that of the reference $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite.

Figure 1. Normalized X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{DA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (B) and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{EA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (C) 2D RP perovskite films.

The detailed evolution of the structure of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite at the different percentage of the A-cation can be monitored through the intense reflection peak around 28.32° associated to the (202) crystallographic orientation and, to a lesser extent, with the peak at 14.04° related to the (111) plane. Figure 3 shows a magnification of the normalized XRD patterns at the (202) peak for all mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites. Importantly, the increase in the content of the A-cation entails a shift in the position of the (202) peak to lower 2θ angles except for Rb where hardly no shift is noticed and for Cs with a shift to higher 2θ angles. It is worth noting that the shift of the (202) peak goes beyond the threshold value previously estimated which we attribute to larger percentages of the A-cation preferentially incorporated into the 2D RP phases with low n values (see absorption and photoluminescence experiments). The shift of the position of the Bragg peak is similar to that previously described in the mixed cation 3D $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite which reveals the incorporation

of the A-cations into the octahedral voids by direct substituting the initial MA cation.⁴³ Thus, the larger size of the A-cations compared to MA (except for Cs and Rb) produces distortions in the crystalline network that results in larger parameters (lower values for Cs and Rb) of the unit cell. The gradual shift of the position of the (202) peak involves a sequential incorporation of the A-cation with an expected growth of the micro-strain in the inorganic framework. The large distortion in the octahedra network produces the rupture of the 2D RP perovskite, i.e. it is not energetically favorable to replace the MA by the specific A cation in the inorganic network above a certain threshold value.

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction patterns in logarithmic scale of the mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites containing Gua (A), DA (B), EA (C), PA (D), Rb (E) and Cs (F) showing only the lower percentages of the A cation up to the appearance of new Bragg peaks.

As previously observed in Figures 1, 2 and S2, new Bragg peaks are detected in the XRD pattern above the threshold value which reveals the formation of additional crystalline phases. Interestingly, the development of the new reflection peaks with the sequential addition of the A-cation obeys the same tendency in all films. Firstly, Bragg peaks at 3.51° and 6.91° are detected which can be ascribed to the (020) and (040) planes of a 2D RP phase with $n = 3$ and BA as the large A'-cations.¹⁸ At increasing content of the A cation, reflections at 4.60° , 9.12° , 13.60° and 27.33° are assigned to the (020), (040), (060) and (0120)

crystallographic planes of a 2D RP phase with $n = 2$ and again BA as the cation located between the inorganic network.¹⁸ The two formed phases may be identified as pure $n = 2$ and 3 phases where the MA and the A cations are combined in the octahedral voids at percentages above the threshold. This assignment is supported by the recently reported synthesis of single crystals of $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{EA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ and $(\text{BA})_2\text{APb}_2\text{I}_7$ with $A = \text{Gua}, \text{DA}$ or FA .^{35,37} Thus, at percentages above the threshold, the A-cations are preferentially incorporated into the octahedral sites of the low dimensional 2D RP phases ($n = 2$ and 3) with a relaxed Goldschmidt tolerance factor.³⁴ The preferential formation of the low dimensional phases entails a reorientation of the 2D RP perovskite with the BA cations perpendicular to the substrate in opposition to the parallel arrangement below the threshold. Finally, at high percentages of the A-cation, Bragg peaks at 6.60° ascribed to the 2D BA_2PbI_4 perovskite can be observed in the films with DA, PA and Rb.¹⁸ Interestingly, the BA_2PbI_4 perovskite is not formed in the mixed A-cation films with Gua or EA, which suggests their complete incorporation into the $n = 2$ phase forming the $(\text{BA})_2(\text{Gua})\text{Pb}_2\text{I}_7$ and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{EA})\text{Pb}_2\text{I}_7$ or the $n = 3$ analogs. Two recently published articles have reported the synthesis of single crystals of the $(\text{BA})_2(\text{Gua})\text{Pb}_2\text{I}_7$ and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{EA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites where the replacement of the MA by the EA or Gua cation significantly stretches Pb-I bonds, expands the cage, and induces a larger octahedral distortion in the inorganic framework.^{35,37} Thus, at high content of the A-cation above the threshold, a decrease in the dimensionality of the 2D RP perovskites is detected in addition to a reorientation of the structure of the crystalline network remaining the BA cations perpendicular to the substrate.

Figure 3. Magnification of the normalized X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns at the (202) reflection peak of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$, (A) $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{DA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ (B), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{EA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ (C), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{PA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ (D), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Rb}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ (E), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Cs}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ (F) and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{FA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ (G) 2D RP perovskite films.

The effective ionic radii of the DA (272 pm), EA (274 pm) and Gua (278 pm) cations are very similar to each other so that the distortions caused in the mixed A-cation crystalline network should be comparable for these three A-cations. However, the threshold value for the homogeneous incorporation of the A-cation into the different n phases and the shift of the position of the (202) peak are not coinciding among them. A larger threshold value is found for EA (30%) vs. DA (10%) with an intermediate value for Gua (25%), but the shift of the (202) peak is more intense with Gua, from 28.32° to 28.27° compared to EA (28.30°), and lower for DA (28.31°) with only 10% of the A-cation. This overall behavior clearly indicates the importance of the shape of the A-cation, in particular the accessibility of the H atoms of the A-cation, to produce energetically stable

structures through the formation of H-bonds with the iodide. Thus, both Gua and EA cations are able to continuously modify the inorganic framework even at high percentages of these A-cations. On the other hand, the DA cation is incorporated into the octahedral voids only at low percentages because after a certain threshold they do not establish the appropriate interactions to stabilize the crystalline network. The higher number of H atoms in the Gua cation or the reduced size of EA cation together with the presence of three available H atoms appear to be the key factors that control the large insertion of these cations in the 2D RP perovskites.

The effective ionic radius of the PA cation (335 pm) is larger compared to the other organic A cations which explains the small amount of PA (5%) that is incorporated into the 2D RP structure before the formation of new crystalline phases. Regarding the inorganic cations, the effective ionic radius of Cs (176 pm) is slightly smaller than that of MA while the radius of Rb (152 pm) is too small for the octahedral voids of the perovskite. It is well-known the formation of 3D or 2D RP perovskites with only Cs but not with Rb.^{12,42,44,45} In both cases, a contraction of the parameters of the unit cell is observed with a very high threshold value (80%) for the Cs cation due to its similar size to MA.

The crystallinity and orientation of the 2D RP perovskite films have also been investigated using Grazing Incidence Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (GIWAXS) measurements examining the effect of the inserted A-cation on the oriented growth of the crystallites. Figure 4 and S4 show the GIWAXS patterns for the mixed A-cation perovskites with percentages below and above the threshold. The ring at q around 1.5 \AA^{-1} correspond to diffraction intensity from the mesoporous TiO_2 substrate at the bottom. In the reference $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite, the analysis of the GIWAXS pattern reveals the presence of discrete Bragg spots around $q_{xy} = 0.9, 1.4$ and 1.9 \AA^{-1} which indicates ordered alignment of the crystals in the film. This preferential orientation of the grain with respect to the substrate is highly beneficial for the charge transport in the optoelectronic applications.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹ The same sharp and discrete Bragg spots are observed in the films with percentages below the threshold (Figures 4B, 4D, S4F and S4J) suggesting highly oriented crystallites in these films. At percentages above the threshold, a sequential loss of orientation in the films upon incorporation of the A-cation is exhibited. The discrete spots become elongated signals (Figure 4C,

S4A, S4C, S4D, S4G, S4H, S4I and S4K) covering a wide range of the q_z parameter. The excess of the A-cation probably induces extended distortions in the structure that are crystallographically shown as a disorientation or increasing disorder in the crystalline domains. Then, we observe a broadening of the Bragg reflections that, in the extreme cases, as the films containing 90% of the EA or 100% of the Gua cations (Figures S4B and S4E), can be evidenced as Debye rings, indicating a randomly oriented structure in the polycrystalline films.

Figure 4. 2D GIWAXS patterns of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A), and three mixed A-cation $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{A}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ with Gua (B), DA (C) and EA (D) perovskite films.

Goldschmidt tolerance factor in mixed A-cation perovskites

The tolerance factor in pure A-cation 3D perovskites allows one to predict the stability of these materials by using just a geometrical parameter: the effective ionic radii of the different chemical species. However, the Goldschmidt rule is not applicable when two A-site cations are incorporated into the crystal lattice of the 3D perovskites. In the next section, we have performed a theoretical study to predict the stability of mixed A-cation 3D perovskites where one of the A-cations

is exceeding the tolerance factor and the other one is MA. Thus, we are interested in calculating the maximum percentage of the A-cation that can be incorporated into the octahedral voids of the 3D crystal structure without producing the collapse of the inorganic network. Obviously, the limit in the amount of inserted cation is imposed by the size and shape of the out-of-tolerance factor A-cation, as well as the size and shape of the MA cation. The results obtained in these calculations can be also applied to the mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskite films since this material is mostly formed by phases with high n values, including $n = \infty$ (3D perovskites).

The insertion of an anisotropic A-cation into the octahedral voids entails the rotation and/or deformation of the octahedra to accommodate the cation inside the cavity. The expansion of the plane containing the longer ionic radius of the A-cation can be produced through different mechanism: increase of the Pb-I distance, octahedra tilting and/or folding of the Pb-I-Pb bond angle (θ) perpendicular to the plane. Here, we assume that the deformation of the cavity occurs only due to a variation in the Pb-I-Pb angle (θ), with a related change in the Pb-I distance in the same axis, but without any modification of the parameters in the other two x and z axes (see Figure 5). However, the expansion of the cavity containing the new A-cation must be at the expense of the contraction of the adjacent cavity, where the MA cation is located. Thus, using only geometrical considerations (see supporting information for more details), it is possible to define two independent Goldschmidt tolerance factors for each of the A (t_A) and MA (t_{MA}) cations which will depend on the deformation in the lattice (Pb-I-Pb angle, θ) and the ionic radius and percentage of the inserted A-cation. Assuming that the limit for the deformation imposes a value of $t_{MA} = 1$, a general expression for the tolerance factor of the A cation can be deduced:

$$t_A = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1 + \left[\frac{1 - (1 - x_A) \sqrt{S_{MA}^2 - 1}}{x_A} \right]^2}} \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

with

$$S_A = \frac{r_A + r_I}{r_{Pb} + r_I} \quad S_{MA} = \frac{r_{MA} + r_I}{r_{Pb} + r_I}$$

where t_A is the Goldschmidt tolerance factor for the A-cation, x_A is the molar fraction of the A cation, r_A is the effective ionic radius of the A-cation and r_I and r_{Pb} are the effective ionic radii of the I and Pb ions, respectively. Equation (1) allow one to obtain t_A , for a given value of x_A and r_A , assuming the maximum contraction in the cavity where the MA is located. For this reason, this equation is only valid for $r_A > 2.325 \text{ \AA}$. Likewise, there must be an upper limit for the allowed values of r_A , which we estimate should be $r_A \lesssim r_I + r_{Pb} = 3.2 \text{ \AA}$.

Figure 5. A) Inorganic network of the perovskite structure distorted with a large A-cation (Gua), the Pb-I-Pb angle is shown perpendicular to the main plane. B) Section of the octahedral cage containing the plane with the larger ionic radius and the geometrical parameters that define the new Goldschmidt tolerance factors.

Figure 6 displays the tolerance factor calculated with equation (1) at a fixed percentage of 25% of the A-cation as a function of the effective ionic radius of the A-cation. It is simple to graph the tolerance factor for a different percentage of the A-cation using equation (1). In case of the A-cations (Cs and Rb) with an ionic radius lower than that of the MA cation, our model is not applicable since the

lattice is not distorted given the low size of the Cs and Rb cations. Figure 6 clearly shows if the tolerance factor of the A-cation is found between the allowed range ($0.8 < t_A < 1.0$) which guarantees the formation of the mixed A-cation perovskite. Thus, Figure 6 indicates that the PA cations are not incorporated to the inorganic network at such high percentage of the A-cation (25%) while the Gua, EA, DA and FA cations can be inserted into the octahedral voids with that percentage. Our experimental results are in good agreement with the calculated tolerance factor except for the DA cation. The estimate of the threshold value of the A-cation calculated from equation (1) that can be included into the voids is 26%, 28%, 50% and 15% for the Gua, EA, FA and PA cations, respectively. As it is observed, the experimental values are closely related to those deduced from the X-ray diffraction, absorption and PL measurements. These results demonstrate the validity of the new method to calculate the tolerance factor in mixed A-cation perovskites. The case of the DA cation is intriguing since the effective ionic radius of 272 pm would involve a threshold value of around 30% for the A-cation but the experimental value is close to 10%. The large deviation in the estimate value might be related to the position of the ammonium group in the molecule, which dictates a dipole moment parallel to the C_2 axes. In the EA and PA cations, the dipole moments extend along the N-C-C atoms, perpendicular to that in DA. The positive charge in the DA cation is less accessible to compensate the negative charge of the I⁻ ions which may affect the stability of the inorganic network at high DA concentration.

Figure 6. Theoretical values (blue line) of the tolerance factor calculated with equation (1) at a fixed percentage of 25% of the A-cation as a function of the effective ionic radius of the A-cation. The red circles display the effective ionic radii of the employed A-cations in the mixed 2D RP perovskites.

Morphological characterization

The morphology of the 2D RP perovskite plays a key role on the non-radiative recombination processes and charge transport in the films.^{50–52} Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) has been utilized to investigate the effect of the insertion of the A-cations on the crystallinity of the films. Figure 7 and S5 show the SEM images of most of the mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites. The morphology of the reference $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite is compact with very few pinholes. A densely packed grain structure is measured with a grain size range from 0.2 μm to 0.7 μm and a practically flat surface. The SEM images for the mixed cation 2D RP perovskites below and above the threshold exhibit similar morphology as the reference film although, in general, with a smoother grain boundaries. This effect is more pronounced in the films with 20% and 60% of Gua and 20% of EA. However, in the films with higher content of Gua (100%) and EA (60% and 90%), we observe smaller size for the grains and the presence of a higher concentration of pinholes. Thus, a moderate percentage of the A-cation (< 50%) seems to maintain the packed grain structure of the reference film. An energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis has also been performed to quantify the elemental composition of the films. Figures S6-S20 display the EDX profile analysis for some mixed A-cation perovskites and Table S1 shows the atomic percentage of C, Pb and I where the Pb/I ratio is close to the theoretical one (0.3) in all films. Moreover, the EDX mapping indicates a homogeneous distribution of the three atoms through the whole film.

Figure 7. Top-surface SEM images of the reference $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A) and the mixed A-cation $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{A}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with 20% of the Gua (B), EA (C), Cs (D), Rb (E), DA (F) and PA (G) cations. Scale bar, 2 μm .

Optical properties

The changes introduced by the added A-cations in the structure of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite can be also investigated by using steady-state absorption spectroscopy. Figures 8 and S21 display the absorption spectra for all mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites where significant changes can be observed in the excitonic peaks at the different percentage of the A-cation in the films. Interestingly, a twofold behavior is detected coinciding with the threshold value estimated in the XRD measurements. At low percentage of the A-cation, the absorption signals undergo barely any change in intensity or in the position of the peaks. Thus, the absorption spectrum of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite film maintains constant up to 25%, 10%, 5% and 15% addition of the Gua, DA, PA and Rb cations, respectively (see Figure S22). In the films with the EA cation, the shape of the absorption remains constant up to 30% but with a gradual shift of the excitonic peaks to lower wavelengths as the percentage of the EA cation rises. A similar shift of the absorption peaks to higher energies has been recently reported in single crystals of the $n = 3$ phase of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_x\text{EA}_{1-x})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite.³⁵ The larger bandgap can be related to an elongation of the Pb-I bond or an increase of the octahedral tilting which seems to be more intense with the EA cation compared to the others.³⁵ Finally, in the samples with Cs, the

excitonic peak associated to $n = 3$ gradually disappear in parallel with the concomitant rise of the signal associated to $n = 2$ (570 nm) and $n = \infty$ (700 nm).

Figure 8. Absorption spectra of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$, (A) $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{DA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (B) and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{EA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (C) 2D RP perovskite films.

At percentages of the A-cation above the threshold value, a constant change in the ratio of the absorption peaks is observed. Thus, the excitonic peak due to the $n = 3$ phase (607 nm) and the rest of the phases with higher n values (> 625 nm) are transformed into the $n = 2$ peak at 570 nm at increasing content of the A-cation for all films. This clearly indicates a preferential inclusion of the A-cation in the $n = 2$ phase due to its ease to release the distortions produced by the A-cation without breaking the crystal structure. Thus, at high content of the Gua, EA or Cs cations, the $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)\text{Pb}_2\text{I}_7$ phase ($n = 2$) is formed with large percentages of the A-cation in the structure, resulting in the pure A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{A})\text{Pb}_2\text{I}_7$ perovskite for 100% of the A-cation. It is worth noting in the films with Cs, the blue shift of the absorption peak of the $n = 2$ phase from 570 to 550 nm (60% to 100%). This elongation of the bandgap is explained due to an increase of the octahedral tilting with the addition of the Cs cations, as it has been reported in nanoplates of $(\text{HA})_2\text{CsPb}_2\text{I}_7$ vs. $(\text{HA})_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$, with HA = n -hexylammonium.³⁶ Finally, in the films with DA, PA or Rb the absorption peak at 570 nm is substituted by the excitonic peak at 510 nm related to the 2D BA_2PbI_4 perovskite ($n = 1$). This result agrees with the Bragg reflections of the BA_2PbI_4 perovskite found at high percentages of these three cations. The crystalline lattice of the 2D RP perovskites with high content of DA, PA or Rb is not able to release the micro-strain introduced by the A-cations and therefore, it collapses producing

the 1D BA₂PbI₄ perovskite. In the films with high content of Cs, a signal at 510 nm is also observed, proving the partial formation of the 2D BA₂PbI₄.

Figure 9. Normalized photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the mixed A-cation (BA)₂(MA_{1-x}Gua_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀, (A) (BA)₂(MA_{1-x}DA_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ (B) and (BA)₂(MA_{1-x}EA_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ (C) 2D RP perovskite films.

The incorporation of the A cations into the structure of the 2D RP perovskites together with the related modification of the distribution of the n phases is expected to affect the optoelectronic properties of the films. Figure 9 and S23 exhibit the normalized PL spectra ($\lambda_{exc} = 400$ nm) of all mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskite films with identical variation of the A cation percentage as in the absorption measurements. The PL peak of the reference (BA)₂(MA)₂Pb₃I₁₀ 2D RP perovskite film (black line) centered at 740 nm is ascribed to phases with high n values close to the $n = \infty$ of the 3D MAPbI₃ perovskite. Additionally, minor PL signals are also observed at 610 nm, 650 nm and 670 nm which correspond to the PL emission of the $n = 2, 3$ and 4 phases, respectively. The higher PL intensity of the phase with larger n value is a consequence of an energy transfer process that funnels the photogenerated excitons to those phases with higher n values.^{53,54} In a similar way to the XRD and absorption measurements, a twofold behavior is also observed with the PL peaks. The initial replacement of the MA cation involves no change in the shape and position of the PL peak up to a certain threshold for each A-cation. This value is about 25%, 10%, 25%, 5%, 15% and 60% for the Gua, DA, EA, PA, Rb and Cs cations, respectively. The previous threshold values are in good agreement with those previously observed in the XRD and absorption measurements. At percentages above the threshold, the increasing addition of the A-cation entails a blue shift of the PL peak in all films and the appearance of multiple PL peaks at high A-cation content, although the

extension of these changes is specific for each sample. The blue shift of the main PL peak at 740 nm is related to the preferential incorporation of the A-cation to those phases with lower n values, preventing the formation of phases with high n values. The larger exciton quantum confinement effect in the 2D RP perovskites with lower n values accounts for the shift of the PL peak to lower wavelengths.^{34,50} In the films with EA, the blue shift of the PL peak from 20% to 40% could be additionally associated to the reduction of the bandgap observed in the absorption measurements which explains the lower threshold value measured in the PL compared to that found in the XRD experiments. In the films with Cs, the minor blue shift of the PL peak up to 60% is explained due to the increase of the octahedral tilting by the inclusion of the Cs cation in the lattice provoking a reduction of the bandgap.^{35,36} As the content of the A-cation increases, the PL peaks move to lower wavelengths ending up with peaks in the 570-590 nm range ($n = 2$) and 610-620 nm range ($n = 3$) and with a peak at 520 nm associated to the 2D BA_2PbI_4 perovskite in the films with DA, PA, Rb, or Cs. All these low dimensional phases have also been identified in the absorption and XRD measurements. The previous results demonstrate that the position of the PL peak can be selectively controlled from an initial value of 740 nm to 520 nm, passing through the different n phases, from $n = \infty$ to $n = 1$. The ease to tune the position of the PL signal by varying the content of the A-cation can be a singular advantage for the fabrication of light-emitting devices with this type of materials.

Figure 10. Time-resolved PL signal at the maximum of each PL peak of $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A), $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{DA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ and $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{EA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite films with different Gua, DA and EA contents. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400$ nm.

Table S2 collects the photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) measured for all mixed A-cation perovskite films. The PLQY value for the

BA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ film is 0.26 % at the very low excitation intensity of 1 mW·cm⁻². The PLQY in 2D RP perovskites is highly dependent on the power density⁵³ so that our PLQY values are in line with those previously reported for low excitation intensity.⁵⁵ The PLQY value depends on the relative concentration of the *n* phases in the 2D RP films, maximizing for *n* = 3, 4 and 5.⁵³ In all mixed A-cation perovskites, the addition of a percentage of the A cation below the threshold provides PLQY values (0.15-0.45%) relatively close to that of the reference BA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ film which is ascribed to the similar distribution of the *n* phases as in the reference film (see the absorption measurements). Thus, the similar PLQY in the films where the A-cations are homogeneously incorporated in the lattice seems to rule out the formation of a large concentration of defects that might promote the activation of non-radiative processes. Upon increasing the A-cation percentage, we observed small variations in the PLQY as a result of the changes in the distribution of the *n* phases except for the films with Cs, where the PLQY gradually decreases (0.07-0.005%) due to the formation of phases with high *n* values (see absorption measurements). In the films with high content of EA or Gua (>80%), the measured PLQY values of 0.03% and 0.07% are attributed to the 2D RP phase with *n* = 2, BA₂EAPb₂I₇ and BA₂GuaPb₂I₇, respectively.

Excited state kinetics

Time-resolved PL decays were also measured with excitation at 405 nm and with a fluence of 1.5 μJ·cm⁻² to investigate the influence of the inserted A-cations on the excited kinetics. The low fluence employed in these experiments allows for the investigation of the monomolecular recombination rate since the bimolecular and Auger recombination processes occur at much higher fluences.⁵³ Figure 10 and S24 display the PL decays of the films at the different percentage of the A-cation including the PL signal for the reference BA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ 2D RP perovskite which yielded time constant of $\tau_1 = 0.29$ ns, $\tau_2 = 1.7$ ns and $\tau_3 = 9.6$ ns ($\tau_{av} = 2.4$ ns) after exponential fit of the data. The PL decays are slightly longer for the films with Gua, EA and Rb but only at percentages of the A-cation below the threshold (see Table S3). In these films, the exciton binding energy is maintained constant due to the same distribution of *n* phases which ensures no changes in the radiative recombination rate. Thus, the longer PL decays may be

attributed to a reduced non-radiative recombination constant because of a decrease in the concentration of trap states.⁵³ In the films containing DA, PA and Cs at percentages below the threshold, the PL decays are shorter compared to the reference $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite (see Table S3) which must be related to a higher concentration of trap states when incorporating the A-cations. The reduced time constants of the films with Cs compared to the reference are in line with the lower values of the PLQYs. At percentages of the A-cation above the threshold, the PL kinetics are much shorter in all films which is assigned to an enhancement of the monomolecular radiative recombination rate. Indeed, the preferential incorporation of the A-cations into the low dimensional perovskite (phases with $n = 2$ and 3) increases the exciton binding energy of the films due to the enhanced quantum confinement.⁵³

Figure 11. Transient absorption spectra at different delay times (A, B, C and D) and time decays measured at different probing wavelength (E, F, G and H) of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A and E), $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{EA}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$, $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.4}\text{EA}_{0.6})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ and $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.1}\text{EA}_{0.9})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400$ nm.

To complete the characterization of the excited state dynamics of the mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites, femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy has been performed for films with A-cation percentages both below and above the threshold value. Figure 11 and S25-27 display the transient absorption spectra at different delay time and the time decays for a selection of the mixed A-cation perovskites upon excitation at 400 nm with a fluence of 45

$\mu\text{J}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The spectra exhibit similar transient features in all films with minor differences related to the relative concentration of the phases in each sample, specially $n = 2$ and 3. Thus, the main transient features observed in the spectra are: (1) a strong ground state bleaching (GSB) at the bandgap, (2) a long-lived photoinduced absorption (PIA) signal above the bandgap, in the 500-550 nm region and (3) a short-lived photoinduced absorption signal below the bandgap, in the 640-775 nm whose exact position depends on each sample. The GSB signal can be assigned to the band-edge population while the PIA signal in the 500-550 nm region is attributed to the renormalization of the bandgap or exciton screening although the absorption of the band edge carrier has recently been raised to explain this PIA signal.^{35,56} Both transient signals display similar long lifetimes connected with the recombination process occurring in the perovskites in the nanosecond time scale. The short-lived PIA signal at long wavelengths is associated to the relaxation of the hot carriers due to the excess energy when exciting at 400 nm. In single crystal of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite, an additional bleaching signal has been observed below the bandgap with a particular growing dynamics.^{35,56} This transient feature is associated to the presence of sub-bandgap trap states which would allow one to identify the influence of the A-cation on the passivation of defects. However, in our transient absorption measurements, we have not observed clear negative transient signals different from those of the GSB peaks.

Figure 11 displays the evolution of the transient spectra for the films with 20%, 60% and 90% of the EA cation with respect to the reference $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite. The all three GSB peaks localized at 570 nm, 605 nm and 640 nm which correspond to the $n = 2$, 3 and 4 phases shift to lower wavelengths in the sample with 20%, proving the effect of the EA cation on the bandgap energy. At larger percentages of the EA cation above the threshold, we only observed GSB signals for the $n = 2$ and 3 (60%) and $n = 2$ (90%) in good agreement with the changes observed in the absorption measurements. Regarding the films containing the other A-cations (Figure S25), we observed similar transient features to the reference $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite at percentages below the threshold (20% of Gua) while at values above the threshold (20% of DA, PA or Rb) the GSB signal of the $n = 2$ phase is enhanced. In case of the films with Cs, negative transient signals associated to the GSB of the phases with high n values

are also identified. Finally, at higher content of the A-cation (Figure S26 and S27), the GSB signal at 540 nm is more predominant which confirms the preferential incorporation of the A-cation into the $n = 2$ phase at any content of the A-cation above the threshold.

A global analysis of the transient decays has permitted to analyze the dynamics of the excited states. In all films with more than one GSB signal, the fast decay ($\tau_1 = 0.25\text{-}0.50\text{ps}$) of the negative transient signal around 570 nm associated to the $n = 2$ phase is kinetically linked to the growing ($\tau_1 = 0.15\text{-}0.40$) of the GSB signal at 605 nm of the $n = 3$ phase. This excited state dynamics has previously been explained due to an exciton energy transfer process which funnels the excitation energy to the phases with larger n values.^{57,58} We do not observe large changes in the dynamics at 570 nm, 605 nm or 640 nm among the films with different percentages of the A-cation with respect to the reference $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite which rules out the impact of the inserted A cation in the energy transfer process. The relaxation dynamics of the excited hot carrier presents time constants in the range of 1.0-1.5 ps.

We have fabricated solar devices with a n-i-p mesoscopic arrangement based on the mixed cation 2D RP $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites as the active layer. Figure 12 and S33 show the J - V curves together with the average photovoltaic parameters obtained from cells containing the different A-cations. The short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) increases in the samples with 10% Gua ($J_{\text{sc}} = 16.78 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) and EA ($J_{\text{sc}} = 14.37 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) with respect to the reference ($J_{\text{sc}} = 13.78 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) while it is reduced in the samples with 5% DA, 5% PA, 5% Rb and 10% Cs. In addition, the average open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) slightly increases in the samples containing 10% Gua and 10% EA (from 0.88 V to 0.93 and 0.91 V) which might be related to a shift of the energy of the conduction and valence bands.³⁹ Regarding the fill factor (FF), no significant changes are observed using the different A-cations obtaining an average value of 0.78. The high and constant value of the FF may be related to the appearance of a small "bump" in the J - V curves which has previously been explained due to the accumulation of surface electronic charge in the TiO_2 /perovskite interface.⁵⁹⁻⁶² The "bump" effect is less intense in the devices containing Gua or DA which could be related to a lower diffusion of iodide ions in these mixed A-cation perovskites.⁶² Thus, there is a clear enhancement of the PCE values of the devices containing 10% Gua or EA

with respect to the reference $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite (from 9.31% to 12.09% and 10.43%) while slightly lower PCE values are observed in the cells using the other A-cations DA, PA, Rb and Cs.

Figure 12. J-V curve of the champion solar cells prepared with the mixed cation $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites with 0% (A), 10% Gua (B), 5% DA (C) and 10% EA (D) A-cation.

Conclusions

The replacement of the MA cation in films of 2D RP $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites by A-site cations which lie outside the tolerance factor range follows a twofold behavior. At low percentage, the A-cations are incorporated into the octahedral voids in all n phases while, at high content, there is a preferential insertion into the low dimensional phases ($n = 2$ and 3). The threshold value between both structural arrangements depends on the size and shape of the A-cation and can be estimated by defining new Goldschmidt tolerance factors that include the distortions in the cage as a function of the Pb-I-Pb angle and the effective ionic radius of the cation. This novel approach to redefine the tolerance

factor in mixed A-cation perovskites is a powerful tool to predict the inclusion of other type of A-site cations in the cage.

The distortion in the octahedra network entails changes in the optoelectronic properties of the 2D RP perovskites. At percentages below the threshold, a blue shift of the bandgap of all n phases is measured in the films with the EA cations which is ascribed to elongation of the Pb-I bond or an increase of the octahedral tilting. The Gua cation increases the PL time constants due to probably a reduction of trap states by passivation. The PLQYs of the films with Cs are strongly reduced due to an intense octahedra tilting by the reduced size of the Cs cations. These results demonstrate the strong relationship between structure and properties in 2D RP perovskites. At content of A-cation above the threshold, the more significant change is the blue shift of the position of the PL peak in all films which is controlled by the changes in the distribution of n phases. The incorporation of low percentages of Gua or EA into the 2D RP perovskites increases the overall performance of the solar devices fabricated with these materials.

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